

MANAGEMENT OF CLIMATE-INDUCED CONFLICTS IN LOCAL COMMUNITIES: A STUDY OF SHIRORO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF NIGER STATE

Ifeanyi Charleston UMENZE

Department of Peace Studies and Conflict Resolution
National Open University of Nigeria,
Abuja-Nigeria ifeanyicc@yahoo.com

Basil O. IBEBUNJO, PhD

Department of Peace Studies and Conflict Resolution
National Open University of Nigeria,
Abuja-Nigeria bibebunjo@noun.edu.ng
and

Marvellous I. OAIKHENA, PhD

Glorious Vision University,
Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Climate-induced conflicts exacerbate significant challenges for local communities that especially rely on natural resources for their livelihoods. It thus becomes imperative to explore the intricate dynamics of climate-induced conflicts and their management in local communities such as Shiroro LGA. The objectives of the study include to: identify the types of climate-induced conflicts in the locality; understand how such conflicts are managed by the local communities; and determine the consequences of the mismanagement of climate-induced conflicts in Shiroro LGA. Using descriptive survey research design questionnaire, data was sampled from 140 residents of Shiroro LGA. It was found the major types of climate-induced conflicts include desertification, drought, farmers-herders clashes, banditry, kidnappings, and land disputes. Such conflicts are managed by the local communities through awareness campaigns of the effects of climate change and insecurity. The consequences of the mismanagement of climate-induced conflicts in Shiroro LGA include increased insecurity and conflict, higher risks of droughts, biodiversity loss, irregular migration, internal displacement, and infestation of crops/animals by pests/diseases. Some of the measures that can be taken to better manage climate-induced conflict in Shiroro LGA include transitioning to low-carbon energy sources, adopting peacemaking initiatives like negotiation, mediation, and settlement to provide lasting peace in the communities, and ensuring adequate security to protect citizens of the Area. The study recommends conducting more awareness programs on climate change challenges at various levels to enhance the local community's understanding. Governments at all levels should make concerted efforts to fight banditry and insecurity in order to mitigate the increasing farmers-herders conflict in Niger State and other parts of Nigeria.

Keywords: Climate change, Climate-induced Conflicts, Shiroro LGA, Banditry

Introduction

Climate change has been a major contemporary global challenge since the beginning of the 19th century (Abaje, et al., 2016). It is manifesting worldwide with a rise in sea levels, unpredictable rainfall, drought, desertification, and a continuous increase in temperature. Experts have projected that the global temperature will increase by 1.4 °C by the year 2030, 2.8 °C by 2060, and 4.7°C by 2090 (Thakur & Bajagain, 2019). It has been defined by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2007), as a statistical variation in either the mean state of the climate or in the variability of the mean state of the climate, occurring over a long time. Climate change usually exposes the environment to several challenges, thereby affecting the economy, health, and agriculture, as well as food and human security (Nyong, et al., 2007).

Like other African countries, Nigeria is seriously undermined by the menace of climate change (Idowu, et al., 2011). Crop and animal production, which are the major economic activities of the country, faces severe failures, including decreasing agricultural production, leading to hunger, malnutrition, and diseases. It is quite unfortunate that, as farmers and herders struggle to overcome high poverty and enhance economic growth, climate change has continued to increase the number of vulnerable people, thereby undermining the prospects of development in the country (Idowu, et al., 2011). The vulnerability to climate change in northern Nigeria is very high. This is mainly due to the rapid advancement of the Sahara Desert (Farauta, et al., 2011). The region is heavily impacted due to the high frequency of drought, increased environmental damage, increased migration, and so on (Farauta, et al., 2011).

Climate change has been adjudged to be a "threat multiplier" as it exacerbates existing vulnerabilities and tensions (Rüttinger, et al., 2015). Indeed, there is perhaps no greater threat to global peace and security, particularly in regions that are heavily dependent on natural resources for sustenance. As Schilling et al., (2014) noted, in localities like Shiroro LGA where livelihoods are closely tied to the environment, changes in climate can disrupt traditional patterns of resource use and trigger competition among different groups. The region is home to diverse people with varying cultures and religions, including the Gbagyi, Hausa, Fulani, and

a blend of other ethnic nationalities in the country. Its geography is characteristic by nature of its proximity to the Niger River and the presence of the Shiroro Dam, makes it a melting point for various activities that can portend conflict due to the increasing scarcity of natural resources.

Conflict is thus prevalent in the locality due to the fact that the economy of Shiroro LGA is predominantly agrarian. This means that most inhabitants are involved in farming, fishing, and livestock rearing and other agripreneurial activities. Additionally, the construction of the Shiroro Dam (which provides hydroelectric power and irrigation potential), has resulted in the displacement of communities. This also accounted for changes in traditional land and water use patterns (Adejoh, 2012). These factors continue to exacerbate the vulnerability of local populations to climate-induced stresses.

Blench (2004), about two decades ago, pointed to farmer-herder conflicts in the region, as a major cause of conflict due to competition over dwindling land and water resources. Similarly, socio-economic pressures have led to Intra-Community (Fiki & Lee, 2004) and inter-community conflicts (Adams, 2016). Consequent upon all these, and also leading to further chaos, are droughts, landslides, flood, that continue to increase force communities' displacement and migration, resulting in tensions with host communities. This often results in armed conflicts between host and settlers. It therefore becomes necessary to investigate this phenomenon, in relations to how the local communities manage conflicts in the wake of multiplier effects of climate-induced conflict.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives have been raised for the study:

- i. To identify the types of climate induced conflicts that are prevalent in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State;
- ii. To determine how such conflicts are managed by the local communities in the study area;
- iii. To assess the consequences of the mismanagement of climate-induced conflicts in Shiroro LGA of Niger State: and

- iv. To proffer solutions on how climate induced conflicts can be better managed in the study area.

For detailed analyses, the remaining sections of the seminar are conceptual analyses of key terms and related literature to show gaps in the study. This is followed by the methodology of the study, which guided the task of data gathering and analysis. Subsequently, the results and analyses of the study were detailed. The study was concluded, and recommendations were offered.

Conceptual Analysis

The concepts of conflict

Conflict is a phenomenon ubiquitous in occurrence and, yet, a diversely-defined concept. Scholars' conceptualisation of conflict is usually divided along the lines of either a general approach or a nature-based approach (Stein, 1976). Pia and Diez (2007) define conflict as a "contest or struggle between people with opposing needs, ideas, beliefs, values, or goals" (p. 2). Conflict, according to Fisher (2000: p. 1), "is an incompatibility of goals or values between two or more parties in a relationship, combined with attempts to control each other and antagonistic feelings toward each other". Similarly, Martin and Nakayama (2013: p. 436), view conflict "as involving a perceived or real incompatibility of goals, values, expectations, processes, or outcomes between two or more interdependent individuals or groups". According to Wallensteen (2002: p. 16), conflict occurs when "a minimum of two actors (parties) strive to acquire at the same moment in time an available set of scarce resources".

Swanstrom and Weissmann (2005; p. 9), who defines conflict as "perceived differences in issue position between two or more parties at the same moment in time", contend that perception should be central to the definition of conflict as a concept because the occurrence of conflict is not entirely based on attitudes and behaviours, but often provoked and sustained by the subjective perceptions of opposing parties. Critical and interpretative perspectives are also used to define conflict (nature-based approach) based on the reasoning

that certain conflicts may be more complicated than they first appear (Martin & Nakayama, 2013).

Concept of Communal Conflict

Ilvento (1995), in his definition of communal conflict, underscored the importance of the locality, interplay and subsistence, which presents an insight into the dynamics of communal lifestyles. As an example, human beings inhabit a geographic region and work together, which provides an opportunity for interplay and engenders battle. Importantly, even the ubiquity of the current communicate era has now not replaced the fundamental relationship between propinquity and interaction. In this regard, Mulin (1996) notes that conflicts in any social system (society), result from variations in perception, restrained resources, position conflicts, inequitable remedy, violation of territory etc. Communal conflicts arise over the production and consumption of products, socialisation, social control, and social participation (Warren, 1978). Communal conflicts are consequently merchandise of social family members.

Communal conflicts are the danger or action of 1 birthday party directed at territory – rights, pursuits or privileges – of another birthday celebration because of differences over economic problems, energy or authority, cultural values and ideals (Robinson, 1989; Coleman, 1957). It has been posited within the literature that maximum communal conflicts are specifically financial issues, of which land represents approximately 90% (See Otite and Albert, 1999).

Concept of Climate Change

Climate change may be described as the observable and sizeable changes in weather conditions, especially in global environments over similar time intervals (Ebele & Emodi, 2016; Ladan (2014). It is the intense reaction of climate phenomena with terrible influences on natural and human resources. Climate trade is perceived in bad lights as it's far regularly followed by environmental crises together with boom and reduction in rainfall activities resulting in floods, droughts and land slides, melting of polar ice-caps, thermal enlargement, surges and acidification of oceans and result to oceanfront flooding. The

ensuing natural failures along with hurricanes, bushfires fires and landslides reasons financial losses, population displacement, communal crises, forced migration, growing ecological refugees, desertification and wide unfold soil erosion. (Edowu, 2011).

The present-day scientific proof shows that human activities are causing interference at specific levels in the international climate and availability of herbal assets, and lots of authors already relate water scarcity to the multiplied chance of violent struggle, in particular in rural societies on the African continent. Climate disruptions because of weather change are reflected on a local and local scale, and the greatest influences are already being felt within the poorest areas of the planet. Nigeria, Africa's most populous country, has been dealing with environmental issues in its territory that may be related to climate exchange, such as growing temperatures, decreased rainfall and advancing desertification.

Literature Review

Rüttinger et al. (2015) studied the relationship between climate change and conflict and noted that it is multifaceted and context-specific. According to him, climate change acts as a "threat multiplier," thereby exacerbating existing social, economic, and environmental stresses. Effects of this are visible in localities like Shiroro LGA, where there is a huge reliance on agriculture, fishing, and livestock rearing. The significant impact climate change can have on agricultural productivity was highlighted by Muller et al. (2011). Such fluctuations in precipitation and increasing temperatures adversely affect crop yields across Sub-Saharan Africa. It also leads to reduced agricultural productivity, resulting in undermining food security and economic stability for farming communities such as Shiroro LGA. Muller et al. (2011) opined that the lack of access to climate-resilient agricultural practices exacerbates these vulnerabilities, making it nearly impossible for farmers to adapt to changing conditions.

Onyema (2019) examined how altered flow patterns of the Niger River, exacerbated by the Shiroro Dam, have reduced water availability for agriculture, fishing, and domestic use. This scarcity has intensified competition among different user groups, leading to conflicts over water rights and access. Effective water management and equitable distribution are

crucial for mitigating these tensions. Water scarcity is a prominent issue in Shiroro LGA, influenced by both climate change and human activities such as dam operations. (Onyema, 2019). Blench (2004) describes climate-induced conflicts as being driven by both environmental changes and socio-economic pressures, resulting in farmer-herder conflict as livestock often encroaches on farmlands due to scarcity of water. In more recent times, this conflict has exacerbated significantly, snowballing into banditry, kidnapping and other such vices. Izom & Iliyasu (2024) investigated the effects of banditry on the socio-economic effects between 2015 and 2021 in Shiroro LGA and found that there is a correlation between climate change, poverty and armed banditry. He also noted that this has a substantial impact on socio-economic activities on the economy of the locality. Umenze, Ibebunjo and Oaikhena (2024), similarly studied the effects of climate change on communal conflicts in Gurara LGA. Adams (2016) notes that extreme weather events, such as droughts and floods, force communities to migrate in search of better living conditions. This displacement often leads to conflicts between migrants and host communities, as the influx of new populations places additional pressure on already limited resources. Effective management of migration and support for displaced populations are essential for preventing and mitigating these conflicts.

Methodology

The research design adopted to carry out this study is a descriptive survey. This research design provides an efficient and accurate means of gathering primary data in view of the population of interest. As indicated, the study area is Shiroro LGA in Niger State, Nigeria. Shiroro is a local government area located in Niger State, Nigeria. It is situated in the north-central part of the country and is known for its natural resources and hydroelectric power generation. Shiroro is located in the northeastern part of Niger State, bordering Kaduna State to the north. It is approximately 100 kilometres north of Minna, the capital of Niger State.

One of the notable features of Shiroro is the Shiroro Dam, which was constructed on the Kaduna River. The dam is a major source of hydroelectric power generation in Nigeria. It has a capacity of 600 megawatts and contributes significantly to the country's electricity

supply. Apart from its role in power generation, Shiroro is rich in natural resources. The Area is known for its mineral deposits, including tantalite, granite, limestone, and kaolin. These resources have the potential to contribute to economic development in the region.

Agriculture is an important economic activity in Shiroro. The fertile soil and favourable climate support the cultivation of various crops such as maize, millet, yam, and rice. Livestock rearing, particularly cattle, is also practised in the Area. Shiroro LGA is challenged environmentally as a result of climate change.

Cluster sampling technique was adopted for the study. This technique was adopted because the technique was carried out based on size and proportions of the population in Shiroro Local Government Area. Therefore, the researcher followed the appropriate cluster groups, which are the residents of Shiroro in some selected wards and communities in the local government. The study clustered the most affected communities within Kuta the headquarters of the Local Government Area. In the second stage, in order to reduce the sample population, the researcher clustered Kuta, Allawa, Bangajiya, Ubandoma and Gurmana by using a simple random sampling technique.

The projected population of Shiroro Local Government Area, according to the National Population Commission NPC (2023), is 404,200. Using Taro Yamane's formula, $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$, the sample size was determined to be 140. Thus, 140 residents of Shiroro LGA were sampled.

Results and Analyses

The primary data instruments in the study were questionnaires used in gathering information from residents of Shiroro LGA of Niger state. However, 140 questionnaires were administered to the respondents, but 127 were returned. Eight questionnaires were not correctly filled, while the remaining five questionnaires were not returned. Therefore, the data analyses were based on the 127 questionnaires that were correctly filled and returned.

Research Objective 1: Types of climate induced conflicts in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State

Table1: Types of climate induced conflict in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State

State	SA	A	D	SD	X	Sd	Decision
1. Desertification and drought	65	44	13	6	2.89	0.817	Agree
2. Farmers and Herders conflict		50	47	19	11	2.80	0.808
							Agree
3. Banditry and kidnappings	72	48	5	2	3.05	0.939	Agree
4. Land disputes	42	45	23	17	2.63	0.647	Agree
					2.99	0.914	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows mean scores of 2.99, 2.80, 3.05 and 2.63 in support of the types of climate induced conflict in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State for items 1, 2, 3 and 4. The overall mean scores of 2.99 and a standard deviation of 0.914, respectively to indicate that the major types of climate induced conflicts in Shiroro Local Government include desertification and drought, farmers-herders conflicts, banditry and kidnappings and land disputes.

Research Objective 2: How local communities climate-induced conflicts

Table 2: Management of climate-induced conflicts in the community

Management of climate conflict	SA	A	D	SD	X	Sd	Decision
1. More awareness of the effects of climate change and insecurity	52	51	16	8	2.90	0.940	Agree
2. Nurturing the development of humanitarian-peace partnerships for end-to-end action at the local levels	59	56	10	2	2.96	0.958	Agree
3. Adoption of alternative Conflict							

Resolution Strategies to address the

root causes of communal conflict. 51 43 20 13 2. 87 0. 863

Agree

4. Involving local vigilante groups to curb the challenges of insecurity in the community.

45 37 32 13 2. 73 0. 758 Agree

2.93 0.974 Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 8 shows mean scores of 2.90, 2.96, 2.87 and 2.73 in support of the ways that climate induced conflict are managed by the local communities in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State for items 1, 2, 3 and 4. The overall mean scores of 2.93 and a standard deviation of 0.974 respectively, indicate that climate induced conflict are managed by the local communities in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State by creating more awareness on the effect of climate change and insecurity, nurturing development humanitarian-peace partnerships for end-to-end action at the local levels, adoption of alternative Conflict Resolution Strategies to address the root causes of communal conflict and involving local vigilante groups to curb the challenges of insecurity in the community

Research Objective 3: The consequences of the mismanagement of climate induced conflicts in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State Table 2: Consequences of mismanagement of climate-induced conflicts in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State

Consequences of mismanagement of climate conflict

	SA	A	D	SD	X	Sd	Decision
1. Increase in insecurity and conflicts	53	51	16	7	2.80	0.846	Agree
2. Increasing risk of biodiversity loss		59	46	18	4 2.	85 0.	858 Agree
3. Irregular migration and displacement of people	56	43	22	6 2.	75 0.	663	Agree

4. Infestation of crops/animals
 by pests/diseases

45 47 21 14 2. 60 0. 658 Agree

2.82 0.873 Agree

Source:

Field Survey, 2024 Table 8 shows mean scores of 2.80, 2.85, 2.75 and 2.60 in support of the consequences of the mismanagement of climate induce conflicts in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State for items 1, 2, 3 and 4. The overall mean scores of 2.82 and a standard deviation of 0.873 respectively, indicate that the consequences of the mismanagement of climate induce conflicts in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State include an increase in insecurity and conflict, increasing risk of biodiversity loss, irregular migration and displacement of people and infestation of crops/animals by pests/diseases.

Research Objective 4: How climate-induced conflicts in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State can be better managed

Table 3: Measures that can be taken to better manage climate induce conflict in Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State

Better management of climate induced conflict	SA	A	D	SD	X	Sd	Decision
1. Transitioning to low-carbon energy sources	54	46	14	13	2.90	0.944	Agree
2. Adoption of peacemaking initiatives like negotiation, mediation, and settlement to provide a lasting peace in the communities		57	53	10	7 2.	95 0.	948 Agree
3. Government at various levels should meet with relevant stakeholders to address the effect of climate change to control the movement of cattle.	58	51	13	5 2.	96 0.	963	Agree
4. There should be adequate security to protect citizens of the Area.	49	39	21	18 2.	85 0.	853	Agree
					2.92	0.973	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 projects a mean score of 2.90, 2.95, 2.96 and 2.85 in support of the measures can be taken to better manage climate induce conflict in Shiroro LGA of Niger State for items 1, 2, 3 and 4. The overall mean scores of 2.92 and a standard deviation of 0.973 respectively to indicate that some of the measures include transitioning to low-carbon energy sources, adoption of peacemaking initiatives like negotiation, mediation, and settlement to provide a lasting peace in the communities, the need for government at various levels should meet with relevant stakeholders to address the effect of climate change to control the movement of cattle and there should be adequate security to protect citizens of the Area.

Discussions on Major Findings

The study revealed that the major types of climate-induced conflicts in Shiroro LGA include farmers-herders conflict, banditry, kidnappings and land disputes. As can be seen from our data, the causes of communal conflict in the study area align with Udoh (2016) and Izom & Iliyasu (2024). This coincides with the report of Ubelejit (2016), who stated that conflicts between farmers and herders have engulfed many communities in Nigeria. Even though studies such as Babajo, et al. (2018), have shown that the people in the Area are into many occupations like farming, animal rearing and trading of agricultural products, conflicts have rendered many of them jobless. However, in the case of Shiroro LGA, climate-induced conflict is further exacerbated by activities of bandits, who raid and destroy farm and arable lands, rustle cattle and put further pressure on the available land resources, causing farmers and herders to compete violently for the available natural resources.

The study found that climate-induced conflicts are managed by the local communities in Shiroro LGA through the creation of more awareness of the effect of climate change and insecurity, nurturing the development of humanitarian-peace partnerships for end-to-end action at the local levels, adoption of alternative Conflict Resolution Strategies to address the root causes of communal conflict and involving local vigilante groups to curb the challenges of insecurity in the community. This is in agreement with the findings of Abaje, (2016) that the impact of climate change requires more awareness at various levels to mitigate its effect on society. The study revealed that the consequences of the mismanagement of climate-induced conflicts in Shiroro

LGA include an increase in insecurity and conflict, increasing risk of droughts and biodiversity loss, irregular migration and displacement of people and infestation of crops/animals by pests/diseases. Ukamana (2017) supported the notion that the likelihood that climate effects will lead to violent conflict depends on the context, as well as on the likelihood that communal conflicts will occur in areas of natural resource scarcity.

The study found that some of the measures that can be taken to better manage climate-induced conflicts in Shiroro LGA of Niger State include transitioning to low-carbon energy sources, adopting peacemaking initiatives like negotiation, mediation, and settlement to provide lasting peace in the communities, the need for government at various levels should meet with relevant stakeholders to address the effect of climate change to control the movement of cattle and there should be adequate security to protect citizens of the Area. Schilling et al. (2014) proposed community-based natural resource management (CBNRM) as a strategy for mitigating climate-induced conflicts. This involves the establishment of community committees that will oversee resource allocation and mediate disputes when they arise. According to them, this approach tends to promote local ownership, accountability, enhances cooperation, thereby reducing tensions (Schilling et al., 2014).

Conclusion and Recommendation

From the foregoing, it can be seen that climate-induced conflicts have negative effects in Shiroro LGA, leading to desertification, drought, farmers-herders conflicts, banditry, kidnappings and land disputes. Consequences of the mismanagement of climate-induced conflicts include increased insecurity, biodiversity loss, internal displacement, and the infestation of crops and animals. There is also a connection between the increase in banditry in Niger State, as some residents cannot make a living due to the negative effect of climate change on their communities. The development has further worsened the already bad economic conditions of the locality.

The study thus recommends that:

- i. More awareness programmes on climate change challenges should be carried out at various levels to help sensitise the local community;

- ii. Governments at all levels should make concerted efforts to fight banditry and insecurity in order to mitigate the increasing farmers-herders conflict in Niger State and other parts of Nigeria;
- ii. There should be engagements in kinetic and non-kinetic conflict resolution frameworks to mitigate the increasing farmers-herders conflict in Niger State, Nigeria;
- iv. There is a need for appropriate adaptation measures such as effective water harvesting and its utilisation, as well as the establishment of public ranches with modernised technologies that can restrict movement of herders;
- v. The government should make concerted efforts to address the root cause of any conflict so as to provide a long-term solution to the conflicts in the country;
- vi. The establishment of functional national infrastructure for peace as well as supporting other peace initiatives such as dialogue initiatives, faith-based dialogue initiatives, town hall meetings for farmers and herdsmen.; and
- vii. Citizens must learn to live as one, regardless of their ethnicity, religion, class or any other affiliation.

References

- Abaje, I.B., Sawa, B.A., Iguisi, E.O. and Ibrahim, A.A. (2016). Impacts of Climate Change and Adaptation Strategies in Rural Communities of Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies & Management*, 9(1), 97 – 108.
- Adams, W. M. (2016). "Displacement, Migration, and Climate Change in Nigeria's Sahel Region." *Environmental Migration Review*, 2(1), 45-59.
- Adejoh, I. (2012). "The Impact of Shiroro Dam on the Agricultural Development of Shiroro Local Government Area of Niger State, Nigeria." *Journal of Environmental Studies*, 7(3), 120-135.
- Ebele, N. E. and Emodi, N. V (2016). Climate Change and Its Impact in Nigerian Economy, *Journal of Scientific Research & Reports*, 10(6): 1-13.
- Farauta, B.K., Egbule, C.L., Idrisa Y.L. and Agu, V.C. (2011). Farmer's perceptions of climate change and adaptation strategies in northern Nigeria: An empirical assessment. African Technology Policy Studies Network. Research Paper No. 15. Retrieved from <http://www.atpsnet.org/Files/rps15.pdf>.
- Idowu, O.B.A., Omirin, M.M. and Osagie, J.U. (2011) Outsourcing for Sustainable Waste Disposal in Lagos Metropolis: Case Study of Agege Local Government, Lagos. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, Vol. 4, 116-131.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (2007). Climate Change 2007, Synthesis Report Summary for Policy Makers. Available at: <http://www.ipcc-wg1-report-htm.pp1-15>.
- Izom, Y.D. & Iliyasu, M. (2024). Assessment of Rural Banditry and Socio-Economic Implication in Niger State: A Focus on Shiroro Local Government Area Niger State, 2015-2021, *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, Vol. 8(3), March: 627-635.
- Martin, J. N., & Nakayama, T. K. (2013). *Intercultural communication in contexts*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Muller, C., Cramer, W., Hare, W. L., & Lotze-Campen, H. (2011). "Climate Change Risks for African Agriculture." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(11), 4313-4315.
- Onyema, E. M. (2019). "Water Scarcity and Conflict Management in Shiroro LGA, Niger State, Nigeria." *International Journal of Water Resources Development*, 35(5), 771-785.
- Pia, E., & Diez, T. (2007). *Conflict and human rights: A theoretical framework*. Working Paper for SHUR. Retrieved on October 14, 2016 from <http://shur.luiss.it/files/2008/10/shurwp01-07.pdf>
- Rüttinger, L., Smith, D., Stang, G., Tänzler, D., & Vivekananda, J. (2015). "A New Climate for Peace: Taking Action on Climate and Fragility Risks." Adelphi, International Alert, Woodrow Wilson International Center for Scholars, European Union Institute for Security Studies.
- Schilling, J., Akuno, M., Scheffran, J., & Weinzierl, T. (2014). "On Raids and Relations: Climate Change, Pastoral Conflict and Adaptation in Northwestern Kenya and Southern Ethiopia." *Climate Change and Pastoralism in East Africa: Challenges, Responses and Opportunities*, 10(2), 247-270.
- Stein, A. A. (1976). Conflict and cohesion. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 20(1), 143-172.

DOI: 10.1177/002200277602000106

Swanstrom, N. L. P., & Weissmann, M. S. (2005). Conflict management and beyond: A conceptual exploration. Uppsala: Central Asia-Caucasus Institute.

Umenze, C. I., Ibebunjo, B. O. and Oaikhen, M. I (2024). Climate Change and Communal Conflicts: A Study of Gurara Local Government Area, Niger State-Nigeria. WAUU Journal of International Affairs and Contemporary Studies (WJIACS) Vol. 4 (1) April: 155-163
Yamane, T. (1967). Statistics: An Introductory Analysis. Harper and Row, New York, USA.